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ABSTRACT

Multimedia is content that uses a combination of different content forms such as text, audio, images, animation, video and interactive content. Despite the fact that visualizations are used more and more frequently in informal and formal educational settings, not much is understood about their semiotic properties, how humans process them, and how they can be best designed to learn from the features of the representational formats are modularity, sequentially and modality. Most visualization is non-arbitrary in that the representation and the represented world are linked to each other by means of inherent structural correspondences or even by physical resemblance. Realistic visualizations made people think more about the concrete referent.

KEYWORDS: Multimedia, Teaching and learning Tools, Interactive Technology, Teacher education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Multimedia contrasts with media that use only rudimentary computer displays such as text-only or traditional forms of printed or hand-produced material. Multimedia can be recorded and played, displayed, dynamic, interacted with or accessed by information content procession devices, such as computerized and electronic devices, but can also be part of a live performance. Multimedia devices are electronic media devices used to store and experience multimedia content. Multimedia learning occurs when people build mental representations from words and pictures. As you can see in this definition multimedia refers to the presentation of words and pictures, whereas learning refers to the learner's construction of knowledge.

Multimedia – Definition

Multimedia is a hot topic in current education because it represents the latest technology and introduces into the classroom whole new ways of thinking about curriculum interactions with students and even the nature of learning itself. He elaborates that the meaning of multimedia has changed from meaning nothing to everything. Multimedia can mean any kind of file or document other a text or spreadsheets that have audio/video effects or "an interactive information cafe".

2. USAGE OF MULTIMEDIA IN TEACHER EDUCATION**Power point Presentation**

We can use the power point presentation to teach the lessons in effectively. It consists of many elements. Some of them

1. Text
2. Images
3. Pictures
4. Links
5. Animation and etc.,

CAI (Computer assisted Instruction) Packages

It is one of the individualized instructions. Students can interact with the computer to learn the lessons. These packages are instructional techniques using the computer which follows for individual, individually paced and individualized instruction. Since the computer's behavior is dependent upon the responses of the student. In CAI package, the information is presented in a structured form. It can provide a method of instructions designed for self-directive study. It helps in improving skills or achieving objectives at all difficulty levels. It provides immediate feedback. It saves the unauthentic labour of teachers as well as students.

Mobile learning

Mobile learning is one of the multimedia learning. It motivates to learn latest techniques or knowledge. It provides mobility of learning setting, not restricted to classroom learning. It consists of interactivity of the learning process and we can interact with others. It gives situational aspects of instructional activities.

Smart Classroom

Smart classroom is a new type of classroom which replaced the formal and traditional classroom environments. It focuses on student's intellectual development not mere learning.

Requiring Equipments

A smart class is a classroom that has an instructor station equipped with computer and audio-visual components. Required equipment for smart classroom is as follows:

- ✓ Personal computer
- ✓ Overhead projector
- ✓ Wireless internet access
- ✓ DVD player
- ✓ Smart board
- ✓ Speaker.

These components are connected wirelessly, via USB or serial cables.

E-Learning

E-Learning includes numerous types of media that deliver text, audio, images, animation and streaming video and includes technology application and processes such as audio or video tape, satellite TV, CD-ROM and computer based learning as well as intranet/ extranet and web-based learning. It is use of electronic media and information communication technologies in education.

1. Technology-enhanced learning (TEL)
2. Computer - based instruction (CBI)
3. Computer - based training (CBT)
4. Computer assisted instruction (CAI)
5. Internet – based Training ((IBT)
6. Web – based Training (WBT)
7. Online education
8. Virtual Education
9. Virtual learning environments (VLE)
10. M-Learning

Procedure for adopting Multimedia Approach

Stage 1: Teacher initiates teaching learning activities.

Stage 2: Teacher demonstrates a specific and specialized unit.

Stage 3: Preparation and ground work for students to embark on independent learning.

Stage 4: Give the student's active participation.

Stage 5: integration of theory and practical

Reasons to use multimedia in the classroom

1. Facilitate and develop a community of learners through online ice-breaker activities.
2. Help students visualize difficult concepts of procedures more easily.
3. Scaffold learning through activities enhanced by videos and online games.

4. Make language and culture come alive through the viewing and creation of audio and video instruction.
5. Provide a “menu” of authentic assignment options for students to complete, allowing them to explore and identify their passions and talents.
6. Enhance accessibility through the use of powerful multimedia software tools.
7. Enable visualization of concepts and their connections through collaborative construction and discussion of concept maps.
8. Make learning situated and personal with easy to access information from you and the rest of the world.
9. Help students document and present their learning through authentic assessments.

Benefits of Multimedia

1. Multimedia can be helpful to organize information in meaningful ways.
2. It offers the different learning styles.
3. It allows for self-pacing and discovery.
4. It helps to develop the higher order thinking skills.
5. It provides the ‘anywhere’, ‘anytime’ learning.
6. It helps in developing group and interpersonal skills.
7. It encourages collaborative learning and enhances the interactions.
8. It helps students to learn to think effectively, practice problem solving and decision making.
9. It enables students to represent information using several different media..

3. CONCLUSION

It has been proved by research that multimedia in schools are effective for students to learn both form and with it. The focus is how on media and technology because of their benefits in terms of repeatability, transportability and equity of access. Multimedia help students to construct knowledge actively, work in groups and multi-senses at a time.

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